

A Study on
The Impact of Human Resource Management on Employee Job Satisfaction in
United Commercial Bank Limited

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Letter of Transmittal

Date: 28 February, 2023

M. A. Akkas

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Subject: Submission of a study titled Human Resource Management practices impact on job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited.

Dear Sir,

It is a pleasure to submit my study on the impact of Human Resource Management practices on employee job satisfaction in united commercial Bank. It was a great opportunity to gain practical knowledge and experience. I have tried my level best to make this study as informative as possible. To conduct the study, I have taken interview and studied books and journals etc. To my belief, the knowledge and experience I have gathered during the internship will add value to my future professional life. I have concentrated my greatest efforts to achieve the aim and objectives of the study. I followed your instructions very sincerely while preparing the study. I believe this study will be able to serve the purpose.

Thank you for your kind and valuable consideration.

Sincerely,

Suzana Sharmin

ID: 024-05; 24th batch

Department of Management

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Bonafide Certificate

Certified that this study titled Human Resource Management Practices impact on job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank, is a bonafide work of Suzana Sharmin who carried out the study under my supervision. Certified, further that to the best of my knowledge, the work submitted here does not include part of any other report of dissertation on the basis of which a degree or award was awarded to any candidate before. Date: 28 February, 2023.

M. A. Akkas

Professor

Department of Management

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Declaration of the Student

I, Suzana Sharmin, hereby declare that the study on Human Resource Management impact on employee job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited is a unique dissertation prepared by me after completing a 45 days internship at United Commercial Bank Limited. I also assure that; this dissertation is prepared only for academic requirement and will not be used for any other purpose. It does not convey any information that might hurt the organization's interest.

Suzana Sharmin

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Acknowledgement

At the very beginning, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Almighty Allah who has given me the opportunity to go through the total process of internship and to prepare a report in this regard within the scheduled time.

In the preparation of this report, I would like to acknowledge the encouragement and assistance given to me by a number of people. I am most grateful to my internship supervisor Mr. M.A. Akkas, Professor Department of Management, University of Dhaka for allowing me to encroach upon his precious time freely right from the very beginning of this research work until the completion of my internship. Without the guidance of Mr. M.A. Akkas this path would not have been so easy for me.

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Executive Summary

Human Resource Management is a process of acquiring, retaining, developing, terminating and properly using the human resources in an organization (Robbins and Decenzo, 2010). This definition indicates that Human Resource Management (HRM) is concerned with acquiring the service of people, developing their skills, motivating employees to high level of performance, ensuring and encouraging their commitment. It is a strategic and coherent approach to the effective and efficient management of people in a company such that they help their business gain a competitive advantage. Human resource practice is a method that offers satisfaction for the employees based on their work at different fields (Bekru et al., 2017; Ting, 1997). In addition, many scholars have stated that human resource practices offer positive contribution to employees' satisfaction in various levels of organizations which increase the performance of the worker. The study aims to explore the impact of Human Resource Management practices on employee job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited.

With a firm commitment of the economic and social development of Bangladesh, United Commercial Bank limited started its journey in mid-1983 and has since been able to establish itself as one of the largest first-generation banks in the country. With a vast network of 204 branches the Bank has already made a distinct mark in the realm of Private Sector Banking through personalized service, innovative practices, dynamic approach and efficient Management. Its vision is to assume a significant job in all the financial exercises, trade and industry by putting resources into network development and new innovation adaption to have competitive advantage.

Human Resource Managers perform a variety of functions. Job design and analysis, recruitment, hiring and selection, placement, orientation, training and development, compensation and benefits, performance management, managerial relations, and labor relations are some of the key functions of Human Resource Management. Human Resource Management is designed to maximize employee performance in service of an employer's strategic objectives. It can be summarized as follows: efficient and effective Human Resource Management practices can ensure employee job satisfaction in their workplace.

Finally, it is concluded that, Bank's functions of human resource management are recruitment, compensation, training and development, leave, promotion, also performance appraisal. Their human

resource department takes decision at the time of recruitment and selection process. They take great care about their employees. Banks's human resource management practices are pretty much satisfactorily successful but still have some rooms for improvements.

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Chapter-1: Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Human Resource Management (HRM) has emerged as a critical function in organizations to ensure the strategic alignment of workforce capabilities with business goals. In the modern competitive business environment, employee satisfaction is no longer just a concern for employee welfare but a strategic necessity for organizational success. Employee satisfaction directly influences productivity, loyalty, and overall organizational performance, making it an essential area of focus for HRM practices. This study investigates the relationship between HRM practices and employee job satisfaction at United Commercial Bank Limited. It explores how different HR functions such as recruitment, training, compensation, performance appraisal, and employee welfare impact employees' perceptions of their job and workplace. By doing so, this research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of HRM's role in fostering a satisfied and motivated workforce.

1.2 Statement of Problem

This is a cross-sectional study, where we measured the outcome and the exposure in the study participants at the same time. A single source of data is used in this study, so the common method bias is not a pervasive topic. In this report, only job satisfaction used as a dependent variable. Job involvement, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, employee engagement, job Performance is not used. This study explores the impact of Human Resource Management practices on job satisfaction in united commercial Bank Ltd. which will provide with the necessary practical implications.

1.3 Rationale of the Study

An important consequence of the study will be that bank will focus on improving human resource management practices to enhance employee job satisfaction in their bank. Employee perception surveys will help the bank to understand employee's needs and develop effective policies to address this. This report will help bank employer to identify employees' attitude at their workplace. It can be recommended that more emphasis should be placed on these human resource management practices to make sure employees job satisfaction and thereby to enhance their commitment and performance. Job rotation should be designed with care. An optimal training plan lets the employee draw on the skills he has acquired at each job rotation stage. Attractive and competitive compensation packages should be equally distributed to their employees, with incentives and rewards offered. Selection and recruitment should be completely unbiased and based purely on merit.

1.4 Objective of the Study

Main objective:

- To explore the impact of HRM practices on employee job satisfaction.

Specific objectives:

- To investigate the human resource management practices of United Commercial Bank Limited.
- To evaluate the human resource management practices of United Commercial Bank Limited.
- To find out the problems relating to the human resource management practices of United Commercial Bank Limited.
- To identify present situation regarding this matter.
- To identify the satisfaction level of employees.
- To provide some recommendations for formulating appropriate job satisfaction.

1.5 Scope of the Study

United Commercial Bank Limited is a well-known private bank and it is working efficiently in the banking Industry of Bangladesh. The study covers the human resource management practices adopted by Bank and the impact of those practices on employee job satisfaction. Bank authority has provided almost all the necessary information for conducting the study. Through this study, efforts were made to find out different functions of human resource management of bank, the result of the human resource practices in term of influencing employee to enhance their job satisfaction level. Hopefully, United Commercial Bank authority will concentrate more on such practices and use effective methods to solve employee job dissatisfaction, which are recommended through the study.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

Some problems faced during the study is mentioned below:

Short Time Frame: The study had to be conducted within a short time frame. For knowing all Human Resource Management practices of United Commercial Bank Ltd. within 45 days internship is not sufficient. So, it is difficult to doing all analysis accurately.

Limited Study Area: The study was limited in one branch of United Commercial Bank Ltd.

Inadequate Information: Adequate information or data is not available and not well furnished. Due to some legal obligation

Other Constraints: The study is done by self-financed. In spite of having shortage of time, data collected by only person and inadequate information, there is probability of getting errors in different stages of data collection, organizing, presentation and interpretation etc.

Chapter-2: Methodology

There are basically four types of study such as exploratory, correlational, explanatory and descriptive. A descriptive study systematically describes a situation, problem or phenomenon, and provides with information about an issue. The primary objective of such studies is to describe and relate existing knowledge to an issue. This study is descriptive in nature. As for this study, the researcher wants to find out and describe the impact of Human Resource Management practices on job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited.

2.1 Data Sources

In order to conduct the study, data have been collected from both the primary sources and secondary sources.

2.1.1 Secondary Sources

Data that is already collected and for which a few calculations are made to obtain certain information is called secondary data. Secondary data is gathered from different sources such as publications, censuses, company internal records, books, websites, journals etc. However, the secondary data sources used in this study are:

- Annual reports of United Commercial Bank Ltd.
- Website of the United Commercial Bank Ltd.
- Various articles and books regarding job satisfaction.
- Information collected from different websites.
- Human Resource Management related books and scholarly articles.

2.1.2 Primary Sources

Primary data is collected by researchers directly from original sources through surveys, interviews, tests etc. Primary data is collected from a source from where the data was generated and is considered

to be the best type of data for research. Primary data can be: Artworks (drawings, movie films, music, etc.), Research by researcher, Books, Surveys and Census, Interviews. The primary data sources used in this study are:

- Survey of the employee in the bank through questionnaire to know their opinion on bank's human resource management practices.
- Practical experience in relevant and required fields.
- Relevant file, notes and manual study as provided by the officer concern.

2.2 Population parameters

A population parameter is a value or measurement, which is a given population, calculated and used as the variable value of another common distribution or frequency function to be defined in that population. United Commercial Bank Ltd. is a company that operates with thousands of employees all over Bangladesh. However, for the purpose of this study, only one branch is considered. The branch of this bank in which the study was conducted consists of 40 employees. So primarily, it can be said that the population size of the study is 40.

2.3 Sampling design and techniques

Sampling is the process of selecting a small number of elements from a large group (population) that becomes the basis for estimating an unknown piece of information, status or outcome about a large group. The sample is a small group of elements that the researcher is interested in. There are basically two types of sampling design – probability sampling design and non-probability sampling design. For the purpose of this study, probability sampling design, stratified sampling has been chosen. Stratified sampling is of two types- disproportionate and proportionate. For selecting sample elements for this study, proportionate stratified sampling will be followed. The procedure is as follows:

Step-1: Identifying elements in the population. There are 40 employees in the United Commercial Bank Limited at Narayanganj branch. The population is $N = 40$.

Step-2: Deciding the strata (k) into which population will be stratified. The employees will be stratified into 3 sub-departments – general banking, general banking advance, foreign exchange.

Step-3: Placing elements into each stratum. 18 employees were placed in general banking, 10 in general banking advance, 12 in foreign exchange.

Step-4: Deciding sample size (n). The sample size is, $n = 6$.

Step-5: Deciding between disproportionate or proportionate stratified sampling. Proportionate method will be followed.

Step-6: Determining the proportion of each stratum in the population (p)

$(p) = \text{Elements in each stratum} \div \text{Population size}$

General banking stratum $(p) = 18 \div 40 = 0.45$

General banking advance stratum $(p) = 10 \div 40 = 0.25$

Foreign exchange stratum $(p) = 12 \div 40 = 0.3$

Step-7: Determining the number of elements to be selected from each stratum = (sample size) \times (p)

General banking stratum = $0.45 \times 6 = 3$

General banking advance stratum $(p) = 0.25 \times 6 = 1$

Foreign exchange stratum $(p) = 0.3 \times 6 = 2$

Step-8: Selecting the elements from each stratum with SRS methods. Here the fishbowl draw technique will be followed.

2.4 Methods of Data Collection and Instruments Used in Data Collection

As a method of primary data collection for this study, questionnaire has been used. Questionnaire is a widely used method of collecting data. A questionnaire consists of a list of questions, which are used to collect data from respondents about their attitudes, experiences or opinions. Both quantitative and qualitative data can be collected through questionnaire. For this study, a list of questions has been prepared. Questionnaires is consisting of close ended and open-ended questions.

For collecting secondary data, different journals, research papers, articles and books and some reports of the organization have been studied. As an instrument for secondary data collection, Google scholar has been used. The research papers and articles were searched by the following keywords: Human

Resource Management (HRM), HRM practices, job satisfaction, impact of HRM practices on employee job satisfaction, HRM practices of United Commercial Bank etc. After searching and collecting the documents, they have been studied and analyzed and then interpreted in this study.

2.5 Data Analysis Plan

To process and analyze the data collected through interview and other secondary sources will be analyzed in the style of grounded theory. At first, the interview data about human resource management practices in United Commercial Bank Limited will be reviewed to define the impact of these practices on employee job satisfaction. Then the data will be re-read, examined and coded. Then the coded data will be placed in categories. After that the data summary, memos and inter-rater reliability etc. will be critically assessed. Then the coding scheme will be revised and lastly the findings will be reported.

Chapter-3: Company Profile

United Commercial Bank (UCB) commensurate its journey as a public limited company incorporated in Bangladesh on 26th June 1983 under the companies Act 1994 and listed in Dhaka Stock Exchange Limited on 30th November 1986 and Chittagong Stock Exchange Limited on 15th November 1995. Continuing the journey with a firm commitment of the economic and social development of Bangladesh, it has been able to establish itself as one of the largest first-generation banks in the country. With a vast network of 204 branches the Bank has already made a distinct mark in the realm of Private Sector Banking through personalized service, innovative practices, dynamic approach and efficient Management.

The Bank has broadened its area of service in different and diverse segments of banking like Retail Banking, SME Banking, Corporate Banking, Off-shore Banking, and Remittance etc. Besides various deposit and loan products of Retail Banking, the Bank caters export and import loan to deserving candidates which in turn helps the overall economy of the country through increased earning of foreign exchange. Other consumer products like UCB Cards have been showing ample success and growth since its commencement in 2006 and soon became the leader in local market with around 40000 card holders. The bank also generates its clients with both incoming and outgoing remittance services. Thus, the emigrants find an easy way to send money through proper channel.

With a firm commitment to promote SME sector, the bank is also evaluating and monitoring business loans, managing business financing risks, pricing products and working for further development of SME. Its Corporate banking service consists of simple business of issuing loans to more complex matters, such as helping minimize taxes paid by overseas subsidiaries, managing changes in foreign exchange rates or working out the details of financing packages necessary for the construction of a new office, plant or other facility. Its area of expertise is in-depth knowledge in financial analysis with analytical capability of financing large project including RMG and infrastructure development projects.

The bank, aiming to play a leading role in the economic activities of the country, is firmly engaged in the development of trade, commerce and industry by investing in network expansion and new technology adoption to have competitive advantage.

United Commercial Bank Limited (UCBL)	
Founded	26 th June, 1983
Commencement of Business	27 th June, 1983
Head Office	Plot - CWS- (A)-1, Road No - 34, Gulshan Avenue, Dhaka-1212.
No. of Branches	221
No. of ATM/CRM	628 (As on 31.12.2021)
No. of SME Centers	2
Off-Shore Banking Unit	1
No. of Employees	5060 (As on 31.12.2021)
Key People	Mrs. Rukhmila Zaman (Chairman) Mr. Arif Quadri (Managing Director & CEO)
Authorized Capital	Tk. 15,000 million
Paid up Capital	Tk. 14,062.366 million

Table 1: Company Profile

Chapter-4: Theoretical Overview

There are a lot of concepts and theories to be acknowledged before going to the depth of the study. The theoretical overview provides a detailed knowledge on different aspects of Human Resource Management and employee job satisfaction. The basic Human Resource Management meaning, functions of Human Resource Management, significance of Human Resource Management, details of employee job satisfaction, relation between Human Resource Management and employee job satisfaction have been studied to acquire a primary knowledge about the impact of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices on employee job satisfaction concepts which will be utilized for further references to practical implications in the study.

4.1 Human Resource Management (HRM)

Human Resource Management (HRM) refers to organizing, coordinating, and managing employees within an organization to perform an organization's mission, vision, and goals. Human resource management consists of recruiting, hiring, training, compensating, retaining, and motivating employees.

The main concern of human resource management is the people who work for the organization. Human resource management basically deals with these people to build a great relationship between organizations. So, organization must concentrate on these human resources to utilize the other resources of the organization. However, it is not easy task to efficiently manage these human resources. It's quite challenging and difficult task as human resources are not identical. They have various personality, emotions, values and perceptions. Moreover, the skills and qualifications of human resources are not constant. Therefore, a human resource manager needs to be conscious on identifying those employees related problem briskly. Logically, Human Resource Management is the strategic and coherent approach to the effective and efficient management of people in a company or organization with the aim that they help achieve competitive advantage over other businesses. Human resource management department responsible for employee recruitment, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation and other benefits.

4.2 Functions of Human Resource Management

Human resource management is the recruitment, management, and development of employees to serve an organization's goals. Human resource managers perform a variety of functions. The main functions of human resource management include:

4.2.1. Job design: job design involves with human resource planning, which is an important task that refers to estimate the size and makeup of the future workforce. Job design refers to the procedure of describing duties, responsibilities and operations of the job. To hire the best employees based on rationality and research, it is crucial to define the traits of an ideal candidate who would be suitable for the job. This goal can be achieved by describing the skills and character traits of top-performing employee, who will be able to fulfill the organizational duties efficiently and effectively.

4.2.2. Job analysis: Job analysis entails with disclosing the job requirements, such as skills, qualification and work experience an employee need. Through job analysis the employer describe the details of job and the knowledge, skills and abilities an employee requires to successfully complete the job. Job specifications describes the qualifications required for the job.

4.2.3. Recruitment: Recruitment is one of the primary functions of human resource management. Recruitment is the process of finding and attracting qualified or suitable applicants to fill vacancies. Human resource management want to obtain and retain qualified and efficient employees to accomplish the goals and objectives of the company. Therefore, the human resource managers create numerous plans and strategies for hiring the right kind of people for the vacancy. They formulate the requirement which can best meet the specific job description.

4.2.4. Selection: it is a procedure of hiring the best suitable employee for the vacancy to ensure the efficient and effective utilization of resources. A human resource manager helps to identify the ideal candidates for interview and selection, who will be able to better meet the job requirements. The candidates are then subjected to a comprehensive screening process to filter out the most suitable candidates from the pool of applicants. The screened candidates are then taken through different interview rounds to test and evaluate their skills, knowledge and work experience required for the job position.

4.2.5. Placement and Orientation: placement is involved with the assigning and reassigning of responsibilities to an employee. It may be in various forms such as promotion, transfer, demotion and termination. After placement, it is required that a new employee should be acquainted with the organization, its culture, rules and regulation, objectives and supervisors and other employees and the procedures of getting them acquainted to their new work place is known as orientation.

4.2.6. Training: it is a repeated procedure of helping employees to perform at a high level. Training is a process of acquiring new skills to do a job properly. Training changes and modifies employee's attitudes and behaviors which will help to ensure the enhancement of their ability to perform a given job. One of the crucial functions of human resource management is to develop the skills and knowledges of their human resources on regular basis. After all, the success of the organization mainly depends on its employee will ensure the utilization of other resources in the organization. Therefore, the success of the organization largely depends on how well the employees are trained for the job and the growth and development opportunities provided by organization to motivate the employee.

4.2.7. Job evaluation: is a procedure of measuring and identifying the value of each job in relation to all jobs within the organization. It is the basis of designing a well- balanced compensation program. The widely used methods of job evaluation are ranking method, classification method, point rating method and factor comparison method.

4.2.8. Performance appraisal: it is a procedure of evaluating the performance of each employee to determine whether their performance is able to meet their job goal. The appraisal procedure consists of six steps- establishing performance standards, communicating performance expectations to employees, measuring actual performance, comparing actual performance with standards, discussing the appraisal with the employee and if necessary, initiating corrective action.

4.2.10. Compensation: compensation is the reward or price for labor. The goal of compensation administration is to design the lowest cost pay structure that will attract, motivate and retain competent employees. Compensation in HRM refers to all the monetary and non-monetary rewards an organization provides to its employees in exchange for their work. This can include base pay; variable pay and benefits.

4.3 Significance of Human Resource Management

Effective exploitation and utilization of nation's natural, physical and financial resources depend on efficient and committed human resource. The development of a country is ensured by skilled and developed human resource. For an organization effective HRM leads to the attainment of its goal efficiently and effectively. In simple words, Human Resource Management (HRM) is a management function that helps line managers to select, hire, train and develop employees for an organization. The following are the contribution of human resource management-

1. Human resource management entails acquiring, training and developing, maintaining and remunerating best qualified employee for an organization.
2. Development of all the employees of the organization by increasing required skills and right aptitude through training, development, performance appraisals program.
3. Optimum utilization of existing human resources ensured by human resource management.
4. Human resource management additionally guide to enhance quality of working life; effective team work is also ensured among all the employees by maintaining the healthy working environment.
5. Personal development of an employee is ensured by providing them various career development opportunities.
6. Promoting employee involvement with the organization by motivating them to work for the organization.
7. Human resource management help to achieve the overall organizational goal by utilizing its human talents.
8. Human resource management ensures the best productivity of the organization by qualitative and quantitative planning of organization's human resources.

4.4 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction allude to an employee's tenderness towards his job, which may act as a motivational factor to carry out all his work responsibilities properly. Hoppock (1998) describes job satisfaction as, "Any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause any person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job". Job satisfaction of an employees affected by several policy of the organization. For instance- compensation and benefits offered by the

organization, overall work environment of the organization where they can easily concentrate on their work and get enough opportunities to develop their career, working with an efficient team members and manager who may cooperate in their work and provide a proper guideline to accomplish their task, current job impact on personal life also influences their job satisfaction. Employee contentment toward their job may be influenced by different situations. In the same organizations, under the same rules and regulations, all employees are not contented with their job. It may vary from person to person. So, the organization must be careful in analyzing their employee job tenderness towards their job.

Smith, Kendall and Hulin have recommended that there are five factors of the job which may represent the most crucial criteria of measuring employee job satisfaction, these dimensions are stated below-

i) Work itself: employee will feel motivated if they feel that their task is meaningful and through their job, they can actually utilize their skills and knowledge. So, making employee motivated they should be given interesting task which may create value of the job in their mind.

ii) Salary: salary is not really the motivator factors but every employee wants to be paid fairly. Without fair salary and compensation system employee will be dissatisfied in their job. If the employee feel they are getting enough remuneration against their job they will remain satisfied.

iii) Promotion opportunities: all employee should be given equal opportunity for their career development. This will help to motivate employee to value their job. Every employee wants to be recognized for their job.

iv) Supervision: proper supervision can make employee aware of their job and provide technical assistance in the completion of their responsibilities. A good supervisor must have leadership skill and need to treat all employees equally.

v) Co-Employees: relationship with the colleagues is a very crucial factor of job satisfaction. If coworkers are not cooperative, it will create disrupt in the way of employee work. Every employee needs to socialize as it is a human need. So, employees should be cooperative. They should complete the task by team work avoid any kind of offensive comments and attitudes towards their coworkers.

4.5 Job Satisfaction Theories

Many scholars around the world develop different theories on job satisfaction. Amongst those theories three major theories are described below-

i) Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory: Herzberg states in this theory that there are two factors of job, one is motivators and other one is hygiene factors may influence the satisfaction level of the employee. Motivator factors help to encourage the employee in their job. Motivator factors are recognition, reward, responsibility, promotion and growth have potential to generate job satisfaction. On the other hand, hygiene factors are salary, job security, working environment, relations with the superiors and colleagues, performance appraisal, compensation and other benefits etc. These factors are not able to motivate the employee but absent of these factors may create dissatisfaction among the employees. So, it should be present in the organization so as to avoid dissatisfaction from job.

Figure 2: Herzberg's Motivation Hygiene Theory

ii) Need Fulfillment Theory: This theory directs that satisfaction of an employee largely depend on the fulfillment of their needs. So, it focusses on measuring job satisfaction of the employee in terms of getting rewards against their need. Every person has some personal desires which they may want to fulfill through their current job. These human needs are work like a motivator to them. If they feel their needs can be fulfilled by their current job conditions, they will feel motivated and which will

enhance their organizational commitment. Otherwise, they will remain demotivated and will not assume the organizational goal as their own goal.

Figure 3: Need Fulfillment Theory

iii) Social Reference Group Theory: Besides these social reference group theory additionally considers the point of view and opinions of the group to whom the employee looks for guidance. Such groups are known as reference group for the employee. In terms of evaluating the various circumstances in the environment and their view of looking the world greatly influenced by the activities of those reference groups. Besides fulfilling the employee desires and wants, if the job is able to provide the proper working environment according to their expectations, they will think their job as worthy.

Figure 4: Social Reference Group Theory

4.6 HRM practices and Job Satisfaction

Human Resource Management practices like- selection and recruitment, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation have a great impact in creating employee job satisfaction. If the selection and recruitment policy is fair then the employee will be motivated. Training and development program can help the employee to learn about their job details and responsibilities. Understanding their own job will help them to carry out their responsibilities properly. Again, all employees want to get recognition for their work. They want to properly utilize their knowledge possessed. So, the organization need to assess the performance appraisal on their work. Providing compensation and benefit may motivate the employee in the organization. If the employee gets enough opportunities for their career development, they will feel more tenderness to the organization. So, human resource management practices and employee job satisfaction have a strong positive relationship with each other.

Chapter-5: Literature Review

Liaison between human resource management and job satisfaction have long attracted the curiosity of organizational researchers. Whether researching human resource management, practices, collision on job satisfaction, researchers have discovered a number of key conclusions.

However, research in this area is still fragmented, making it difficult for researchers to decode the literature's primary conclusions, identify unsolved issues, and chart a course ahead. This literature overview on human resource management and job satisfaction incorporates findings from study in strategy, organizational theory, and behavior, as well as public relations and corporate communication studies. In the literature, we find different basic perspectives like the internal practices of human resource management and employee job satisfaction criteria. We go over key concepts from different point of view.

Human Resource Management

Many scholars around the world gave various definition of human resource management. They all depict human resource management in different way.

Human resource management, according to Robbins and Decenzo (2010), Human Resource Management (HRM) is a process of acquiring, retaining, developing, terminating and properly using the human resources in an organization.

John Storey (1995) describes that Human Resource Management is a distinctive approach to employment management which seeks to achieve competitive advantage through the strategic deployment of a highly committed and capable work force, using an integrated array of cultural, structural and personal techniques.

Dessler (2003) describes Human Resource Management as a process of acquiring, training and appraising and compensating employees and attending to their labor relations, health and safety, and fairness concerns.

Human Resource Management, according to Mathis and Jackson (2005), deals with the design of formal systems in an organization to ensure the effective and efficient use of human talents to accomplish organizational goals.

Micheal Jucious (1984) defined human resource management as the field of management involves planning, organizing, directing and controlling the functions of procuring, developing, maintaining and motivating a labor force.

Senyucel (2009) described human resource management as a combination of individuals-centered management practices that consider workers as assets and are oriented towards creating and maintaining professional and dedicated employees to achieve organizational objectives.

According to Flippo, human resource management is planning, organizing, directing and controlling the functions of procuring, developing, maintaining and motivating a labor force.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a widely research topic around the world. Many scholars gave their own opinion on job satisfaction.

According to Hoppock (1935) states that job satisfaction is combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job.

Vroom (1964) defined that job satisfaction focuses on the role of the employee in the workplace. Thus, he defines job satisfaction as affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying.

Job satisfaction, according to Statt (2004) is the extent to which a worker is content with the rewards he or she gets out of his or her job, particularly in terms of intrinsic motivation.

Aziri (2008) describing on job satisfaction told that “we consider that job satisfaction represents a feeling that appears as a result of the perception that the job enables the material and psychological needs.”

Mullins (2005) describes that,” Job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted concept which can mean different things to different people. Job satisfaction is usually linked with motivation, but the

nature of this relationship is not clear. Satisfaction is not the same as motivation. Job satisfaction is more of an attitude, an internal state. It could be associated with a personal feeling of achievement, either quantitative or qualitative.”

This study looked at roughly 25 sources of literatures and synthesized 12 of them, primarily journal papers that focused on human resource management and job satisfaction. In the subject of human resource management and job satisfaction, the researchers have made significant contributions. It examined previous researches to find out the relationship between human resource management and job satisfaction. This study summarizes that there is a strong positive relationship with human resource management and job satisfaction.

Authors	Title	Objective	Methodology	Findings
Ricardo Peccei, Karina Van De Voorde (2015)	Human Resource Management and Performance	To explore the liaison between human resource management and performance of employees	Empirical Research	Define the empirical evidence concern with the liaison between human resource management practices and employee performance.
Pankaj Tiwari, Karunesh Saxena (2012)	Human Resource Management: A comprehensive review	To build an idea on human resource management practices implemented by different companies	Conceptual Research	Gather idea on external and internal factors which may affect human resource management practices
Jeffry Pfeffer (1994)	The Human Equation	To explore the outcome of high commitment work practices on organizational performance	Empirical Research	Identify the reasons why high commitment work practices, effective ways of managing the employment relation weren't more commonly available.
Vikram jeet, Dr. Sayeeduz-Zafar (2014)	A study on HRM practices on employee job satisfaction in private sector banks	To explore the impact of human resource management practices on job satisfaction of private sector banking employees	Explorative Research	Attempt has been made to assess the relationship between human resource management practices and job satisfaction.

Authors	Title	Objective	Methodology	Findings
Alina Ileana pestrecu, Rob Simmons (2008)	Human Resource Management practices and worker's job satisfaction	To find out the liaison between human resource management and workers job satisfaction and their satisfaction with pay system	Exploratory Research	Different human resource management practices help to enhance the overall job satisfaction level of employee.
M.J. Martin (2011)	Influence of human resource practices on employee intension to quit	To define the impact of human resource management practices on employee job satisfaction, commitment and their intension to quit.	Empirical, Exploratory Research	Momentous affinity between human resource management and employee intension to quit, influencing by job satisfaction.
T.H. Majumdar (2012)	Human Resource Management practices and employees' satisfaction towards private banking sector in Bangladesh	Achieving a clear knowledge on current human resource management practices and its affiniton with employee job satisfaction	Conceptual, Exploratory Research	Dispose that most of the employees are not satisfied with existing compensation and reward policy
Bob Kane, John Crawford, David Grant (1999)	Barriers to effective HRM	To find out the potential barriers in the way of effective human resource management.	Explanatory Research	Defined the barriers and other ineffectiveness of human resource management process.
Peter Prowse, Julie Prowse (2010)	Whatever happened to human resource management	To measure the contribution of human resource management on individual performance	Exploratory Research	Develop an idea on the obstacles of research design in measuring benefaction of Human resource management

Authors	Title	Objective	Methodology	Findings
Stephen Wood (1999)	Human Resource Management and Performance	To investigate the high involvement of management which may guarantee superior organizational performance.	Empirical Research	Identify the importance of lean production and total quality of management.
Fatma Cherif (2019)	The Role of Human Resource Management practices and employee job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment in Saudi Arabian banking sector	To explore the role of human resource management and job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment.	Explorative Research	Human resource management is strongly correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment.
Piyasena, KGCC and Kottawatta (2015)	The HRM practices on Job satisfaction of operational workers in the apparel industry in Colombo District, Sri Lanka	To describe the human resource management practices on job satisfaction of operational workers.	Explanatory research	Human resource management practices have significant and positive relationship with job satisfaction.

Table 2: Literature Matrix

Chapter-6: Analysis and Findings

Through well-defined human resource management practices, organizations can enhance their employees job satisfaction. The analysis and findings of this study illustrates and analyzes the outcomes of the study, the objectives that are fulfilled.

6.1 Analysis of the Study

This encompasses different practices of human resource management in United Commercial Bank Limited which are used for enhancing employee job satisfaction, evaluation of effectiveness and efficiency of these practices on aspects of employee job satisfaction.

6.1.1 Human Resource Practices in United Commercial Bank:

United Commercial Bank Limited is well known commercial bank in Bangladesh, to gain competitive advantage in the banking industry bank make huge investment on improving their human resource management process. They maintain distinct human resource department to procurement, advancement, maintenance, inspiration. To utilize the human asset, they create worker aptitude and information through preparing and improvement. Bangladesh Bank Training Academy (BBTA) and Bangladesh Institute of Bank Management (BIBM) help to develop many officials. Human resource division is embellished to online based to cope up with the changing banking technology around the world.

Human Resource Division's:

Human resource division of United Commercial Bank includes the following activities to ensure proper human resource management:

- Administration

- Recruitment

- Training and development

- Performance appraisal
- Human Resource Information System (HRIS) and strategic planning
- Compensation and other benefits

Selection and recruitment process of United Commercial Bank Limited

Employee selection and recruitment is a crucial portion of human resource management. Putting the best employee in the respective position is the main goal of human resource division. To choose the appropriate employee they follow few standards and arrangements. Selection and recruitment processes are-

1. Making advertisement to call qualified employee for the vacant job position
2. Sending application to the head office through human resource division
3. Select the application according to the required qualification needed for the position
4. Rejecting those application who are not qualified for the job
5. Make primary list of selected applicants
6. Take a written test of the selected applicants
8. Next arrange oral tests for the applicants who passed the written test
9. Issuing the interview card to the selected applicants
10. Completing the oral test through an interview
11. Rejecting candidates who are lack of skills
12. Forming a list of selected candidates to further physical test
13. Accepting the consent of authorities to approve them

14. Collecting the selected candidate's medical certificate

15. Rejecting candidates who have physical problem

16. Finally providing the appointment letter to the candidates who passed the physical test to join the vacant position

Types of recruitment:

• **Direct Recruitment**-Human resource department of United Commercial Bank Limited, collect the applicants curriculum vitae and select from them the most qualified candidates.

• **Promotion**- bank provides promotion based on valid whereas no worker will be promoted based on their seniority they will get promotion based on their qualification.

• **Lateral appointment**- in the lateral appointment, recruiting employee for a vacant position from the inside employee by promoting on basis of seniority or age.

• **Contractual**- here applicants are chosen based on agreement for fulfilling the vacant position.

Recruitment sources: United Commercial bank recruitment policy uses two possible ways of recruitment. One is internal sources and other one is external sources. Through these two recruitments process they want to appoint best qualified employee for the respective job position who will be able to better ensure the bank goal and utilize the other resources of the bank.

Internal recruitment:

Job position – providing employment chances to every existing employee. They will get opportunities to fill the vacant position according to their knowledge and ability. They may fill the higher vacant position by getting promotion to the upper level.

Employee referrals- sometimes new employee may be appointed on the refence of existing employee. Existing employee of the bank recommend the candidate for the vacant position that's how bank don't have to give any advertisement to outside of the company. If the recommended candidate fulfills the requirement of the job, then they will be appointed to the vacant position.

Skills inventories-United Commercial Bank Limited maintain all the representative data through human resource division. They keep record of all the employee's ability, instruction, work history and other crucial data. From this they can later select representative for obtaining a specific work.

External recruitment:

Advertisement and online source: Advertisement is widely used methods of external recruitment. Selecting the best qualified employee in a competitive market advertisement is the best way. Through notice bank can inform about the vacancy of employment position, requirements and other relevant data. Currently the bank is making best use of online Advertisement. The online advertisements are Facebook, LinkedIn, and Bd- Jobs. They also give advertisement in the newspaper in search of collecting appropriate employees for the vacant position.

Internship: Internship provides the opportunities to the candidates to join the bank temporarily. In the mean time they learn all the banking activities. Later they may get offer to join the bank permanently based on their performance.

Salary:

Probationary Officers will get 41,900/- every month and they will proceed waiting on the post-trial process for a time of one year. After the completion of the trial period, probationary Officer will be promoted as senior officer and they will get 52,000/ - every month with a number of benefits. At United Commercial Bank Limited all the employees are rewarded with yearning compensation, which is a motivating force in creating employee job satisfaction and provide enough opportunities to every employee for their personal development.

Training and development

United Commercial Bank Limited make a huge investment on training and development program. Human resource department make effective plan for training and improvement of all the employees. Developing a well-organized training program, bank ensure that the employee may become able to

carry out their responsibilities properly. United Commercial Bank Limited also coordinated a month-long training program for its chiefs. Bank has training and improvement community to prepare the employee in the best manner. Bank's human resource division determine all the training programs for the employees. A number of training program are provided to the employees as per the bank requirements. They try to give best assistance to their employee to fulfill their duties. All the training prepared by human resource division. Bank orchestrate 30-45 days long trading program. Both trial and the executive's student officer present with their understanding after these programs. United Commercial Bank provide Bangladesh Institute of Bank Management (BIBM) training to all the employees.

Employee Training Method:

Employee needs proper training to better understand their responsibilities which may change time to time to keep pace with the changing technology around the world. United Commercial Bank use these two kinds of strategy to train their employee.

- **On-the-job Training:** This is the mostly used training methods. In these techniques all the employees are made familiar with the work in their own departments. Through these types of training employees can carry out their work in proper manner. They can gain a proper knowledge about the working environment and circumstance. In this training procedure employee do the work and they take required help from the chief, groups with the objective that they can better perform their job.

- **Off-the-job Training:** In this training procedure employees are made able to gain their occupation jobs besides their individual work in a single department. Basically, it helps the employee by providing all basic information on banking activities which may help the employee to develop their knowledge about their overall job details. Off-the-job training is somehow expensive. Employees can put more focus on the training as they are given distinct environment for learning on a different perspective.

Bonus and Benefits

Bonus: The Bonus can be given to the employees in various ways. Bonus can be given at constant rate on the basic recompense paid every year and a little to the productivity rate. United Commercial Bank limited provides the bonus to the employees based on great performance. That's why, it is

included along with the salary as a reward. All the employees of United Commercial Bank bounded are entitled for one yearly reward each comparing to necessary recompense under the following cases:

Attendance in the calendar year	Bonus entitlement
200+ days	100%
90+ days	50%

Table 3: Bonus Entitlement

Festival bonus: United Commercial Bank provide two types of festival bonus. One is on EID-UL-FITR and another one is on EID-UL-AZHA. Bank also provide execution base bonus framework.

House rent allowances: House rent allowances may be provided to the employees at such rates and conditions as may be advocated by their designation. This is accommodating the employee with a view to encouraging its employees by giving extra facility to lead a good life.

Medical allowance: United Commercial Bank provides medical allowances to its employee to make felt secured. These medical allowances include medical coverage and therapy. Only one out of every odd worker will be provided the treatment benefits by the bank

Car purchase and loan scheme: United Commercial Bank Limited also provide transportation cost to its directorate. Likewise, directorates are additionally provided driver cost, fuel cost and all necessary upkeeping cost for the vehicle.

Provident fund: All the employees are provided provident fund. The employee dedication equivalent to 10% of the necessary recompense, it reduced every month from the employee's basic salary through the finance department.

Performance appraisal system of UCBL:

Performance appraisal associated with investigating the regular work performance of the employees and their overall organizational commitment by assessing their job involvement. From performance appraisal bank can develop an idea on its employees' attitudes, development, accomplishment and need. It is taken in two years through a promotion assessment exam. Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS), Paired Comparison Method, Critical episodes, Management by Objective (MBO) are several strategies which are maintained by United Commercial Bank Limited to enhance the overall performance of the employee.

6.2 Findings of the Study

The overall analysis dictates that human resource management practices of United Commercial Bank Limited are quite efficient and effective. The findings of this study encompass the relevance of practical human resource management practices to the theoretical concepts.

As discussed earlier, human resource management practices are job analysis, recruitment, training, job evaluation, performance appraisal, compensation etc. in this study I have analyzed the outcome of these functions in terms of employee job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited.

Through a survey I have analyzed 50% of the employees of the bank are extremely satisfied, 33% are somewhat satisfied and 16% are neutral about their feelings towards their job.

In terms of providing adequate opportunities for career development, 66% employees are agreeing that United Commercial Bank Limited offer proper chance for development. The rest of the employee neither agree nor disagree with this fact.

Another crucial functions of human resource management are training, which help employees to get acquainted with their job responsibilities and observe their duties most efficiently. This is somehow an important criteria of job satisfaction. In United Commercial Bank Limited 33% employees feel extremely satisfied, 50% feel somewhat satisfied and they think there is a huge room for development of training process. The rest of employees have no opinion on the training process.

All major jobs are subject to formal job analysis, 66% employees agree with this statement and 33% are neutral on this statement. Another important criterion of job satisfaction is performance appraisal system which help to improve the employee organizational commitment. In United Commercial Bank 66% of the employees are satisfied and rest of the employee are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

Bank also take remedial measures to manage employee absenteeism by enhancing their overall job satisfaction. However, 65% employee believe that they are getting enough salary which may compensate with their hard work and achievement. 34% of the employee are not that much satisfied with their existing salary.

50% of the employees think knowledge possessed by them is effectively utilized in the job to considerable extent, 33% think to great extent they are utilizing their knowledge possessed, 16% employees have average opinion on the overall enhancement of their job utilization.

Finally, 50% of the employees are somewhat satisfied with the reward and compensation policy of the United Commercial Bank Limited. 33% of employees are extremely satisfied whereas 16% employee think they are not getting enough reward and compensation against their work.

Chapter-7: Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

Human Resource Management practices such as- job analysis, selection, recruitment, training and development program, performance appraisal, compensation and reward may create a great impact on employee which may derive to their high level of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Employees are the driving force for any organization and regarded as human resource, which cannot be replaced by other resources. Through human resource management an organization can best manage its human talents and gain the competitive advantage in the long run. An effective human resource management can help to attract and motivate employees. Fair recruitment and selection, effective training and development opportunities and attractive compensation and other benefit packages enhance the level of satisfaction of employees. If employees are satisfied, they will give their best effort to make the organization more productive.

United Commercial Bank Limited have a well-maintained human resource divisions to ensure efficient and effective human resource management. They recruited on yearly basis which is quite fair. To recruited employee, they use both internal and external recruitment process. Their salary and compensation policy are quite attractive. They provide their employee various incentives and benefits based on their performance, which may motivate them to meet some target in achieving overall bank's goal. United Commercial Bank also work for improving their training program. They sometimes provide 30-45 days long training and also provide short span training. They ensure cross functional training and job rotation to enrich employee knowledge asses the work of employees and provide performance appraisal based on their regular performance, which may motivate them to observe their responsibilities properly. Management by objectives method is followed by the bank to continuously asses the bank performance. Promotion assessment exam is taken by bank in every two years to offer employees career development opportunity.

United Commercial Bank Limited make a vast investment in their human resource management practice. Most of the employees are currently satisfied with the most of the human resource management functions. Bank human resource management practices are quite effective and efficient.

However still they have some room for further improvement in the overall human resource management practices.

7.2 Recommendations

United Commercial Bank is a renowned commercial bank in Bangladesh. Still the bank has some room for further development to gain competitive advantage by developing more employee job satisfaction. It should consider the following suggestions to gain long run competitive advantage in banking sector.

1. Bank may arrange training program on job role basis which may be more efficient implementation of training process.
2. Bank should be more conscious on implementing update software and knowledge development skill to gain productivity of manpower with effectively and efficiently.
3. Online training and exam can be taken in quarterly internal in different topics.
4. Bank should emphasis more on developing a clear human resource strategy.
5. Bank should continuously make investment on making banking methods and technology more adaptive to current banking system around the world.
6. Increase in house training to make employee acquainted to the changing environment and technology of the banking system.
7. Perform and participate different organizational and social activities.
8. Transfer and promotion policies should be maintained in a flexible manner.
9. Interactive session should be ensured to make a foster open communication among all the branches of the bank.
10. Training method should be more properly organized.
11. Promotion policy should be more frequent by assessing employee performance.

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Appendices

Annex 1

A study on the impact of Human Resource Management on job satisfaction in United Commercial Bank Limited

Date: 01.02.2023

Aim: This questionnaire is aimed at finding out the impact of Human Resource Management practices on employee job satisfaction.

Privacy Statement: I am committed to protecting your personal information and respecting your privacy. Personal information is defined as any details that will enable you to be identified, such as ID numbers, telephone numbers, address, email address etc. All of the information that you provide will be treated as confidential and will only be used for research purposes. Your comments will not be identified as belonging to you, instead they will be combined with those gathered from other respondents, and will be analyzed as part of a group. I will not use any of the information you provide for any non-research activities.

Respondent's Information:

Name	Designation	Department
Md. Mainuddin	Senior Officer	General Banking
Md. Naimul Islam	Assistant Cash officer	General Banking
Shangida Aktar Dola	Junior Officer	General Banking
Hafez Ahmed	Senior Officer	General banking Advance
Kazi Meherun Nessa	Senior Executive Officer	Foreign Exchange
Md. Motasim Billah	Executive Officer	Foreign Exchange

Questions:

1. Personal details:

a) Name :

b) Designation :

2. How satisfied are you working for the bank?

a) Extremely satisfied

b) Somewhat satisfied

c) Neutral

d) Very dissatisfied

e) Extremely dissatisfied

3. Does United Commercial Bank offer adequate opportunities for career development?

a) Agree

b) Neutral

c) Disagree

4. Are you satisfied with the investment bank makes training?

a) Extremely satisfied

b) Somewhat satisfied

c) Neutral

d) Dissatisfied

5. All major jobs are subject to formal job analysis

a) Agree

b) Neutral

c) Disagree

6.Performance appraisal system is extended to all members of the organization

- a) Agree
- b) Neutral
- c) Disagree

7.Is the remedial measures taken by bank to manage employee absenteeism?

- a) Yes
- b) No

8.Does your salary compensate with your hard work and achievement?

- a) Yes
- b) No

9.Do you think knowledge possessed by you is effectively utilized in the job?

- a) To great extent
- b) To considerable extent
- c) Average
- d) To little extent

10.Does reward and compensation policy is satisfactory?

- a) Extremely satisfied
- b) Somewhat satisfied
- c) Neutral
- d) Dissatisfied

11.Please make your suggestion to improve the overall Human Resource Management practices of Bank?